

Case study - DANUBIUS-RI institutions present in multiple RIs – status of the DANUBIUS-RI components in the context of the European research infrastructures

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Abstract:	This deliverable contains the results from a first set of an internal landscape analysis to ensure compatibility of DANUBIUS-RI with other RIs and a use case on the contribution of CNR-ISMAR to the I-STORMS project in terms of solving interoperability challenges.		
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Scope of the document

This document focuses on the harmonization of DANUBIUS-RI implementations within the research infrastructure (RI) ecosystem through an internal landscape analysis of the links of the DANUBIUS-RI institutions to other RIs (in particular DANUBIUS-RI components in the context of the European RIs) via a PID approach, an internal questionnaire on interoperability experience and the involvement of the DANUBIUS-RI components in the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) interoperability questionnaire. A Use Case based on the Modelling Node CNR ISMAR is presented to draw further recommendations and best practices to follow to increase interoperability and ensure compatibility of DANUBIUS-RI implementations with other RIs.

Executive Summary

The landscape of European research infrastructures (RIs) is growing and with it, heterogeneity of numerical services at every level (e.g. standards, data, services). One major challenge at the European scale is increasing interoperability capabilities to harmonise this heterogeneous RI landscape and establish synergies and strong links between RIs. This document presents the results from a first set of an internal landscape analysis to ensure compatibility of DANUBIUS-RI with other RIs. It focuses on the DANUBIUS-RI components and their links to other European RIs and a use case with the aim of providing recommendations from the component involvement and experiences in other more advanced RIs (in terms of implementation stage) for the harmonisation of DANUBIUS-RI implementations. The overall goal of the internal landscape analysis is to provide a snapshot of the status, experience and literacy in interoperability of the DANUBIUS-RI components in the context of the European RIs at the time of its implementation. We developed a simplified PID graph inspired by the PID graph (work-in-progress, FREYA, OpenAIRE) showing links between DANUBIUS-RI institutions and other RIs through common publications using DOIs (Fig.1). The results showed that half of the researchers displayed links with European projects through PIDs but their links to other RIs varied greatly: 3 researchers from 2 institutions had more than 19 links with 2 other RIs (JERICO and RECETEX) and from one of these institutions, 2 other researchers have 11 and 13 links with respectively ICOS and ACTRIS. All the remaining researchers and institutions had fewer than 5 links with JERICO, ICOS, LifeWatch ERIC, eLTER, HYDRALAB, EUXINUS (the Romanian contribution to EMSO-ERIC). The next step was an internal survey to identify common interoperability issues, challenges and current practices in the European RI ecosystem through feedbacks from DANUBIUS-RI institutions. When inquired about the interoperability challenges they faced in other RIs and projects, the most cited concepts were related to technical challenges and data. Our internal questionnaire also highlighted a gap in interoperability literacy with 3 participants answering that they had never had to deal with any type of interoperability including partners involved in data management. Finally, the use case focused on one of the partners of the DANUBIUS-RI Modelling Node - CNR ISMAR and their contribution to the I-STORMS project in terms of developing the software infrastructure named *I-STORMS web systems (IWS)*. Challenges CNR-ISMAR faced in this project were of technical nature. Their solutions to overcome these challenges were based on partners' involvement at all phases, common data policy, common agreed data structure and codes and custom software development. These internal analyses showed that achieving interoperability is a complex task that involves various challenges, ranging from

understanding what the different type of interoperability involves conceptually, to technical and societal challenges of its successful implementation in practice. This complexity needs to be tackled at different scales: at the European scale, DANUBIUS-RI will need to deploy some of the EOSC interoperability guidelines to achieve interoperability to integrate its resources (e.g. data, services) within the EOSC-Core. Finally, more human resources such as data steward, working group and committee such as the one we created for DANUBIUS-IP in WP2, are required at the RI level, to grasp each RI specificity and challenges to link it with the national and European efforts to improve interoperability and harmonise the European RI landscape.

Introduction

Technological advancements have made research and science more data intensive and interconnected, with researchers producing and sharing increasing volumes of data. One major challenge for the growing European Research infrastructures (RI) landscape is how to create joined-up ways of producing, sharing and using data, services and standards in other words increase interoperability between them at all levels.

The European interoperability model defines interoperability as “the ability of organisations to interact towards mutually beneficial goals, involving the sharing of information and knowledge between these organisations, through the business processes they support, by means of the exchange of data between their ICT systems”¹. The European interoperability model further recognizes 4 layers of interoperability (SOURCE):

1. *Technical Interoperability (TI)* which refers to communication protocols and infrastructures required to enable machine-to-machine communication. TI is achieved among communications-electronics systems or items of communications-electronics equipment when services, data or information can be exchanged directly and satisfactorily between them and their users;
2. *Semantic interoperability (SI)* which is defined as the ability to exchange data and information while ensuring that their precise format and meaning is preserved and understood throughout exchanges between parties: “what is sent is what is understood”; Semantic interoperability refers to how data items are described and mapped across different information systems in order to minimise ambiguity and ensure the adequate interpretation of individual data items. In this context, developing common vocabularies and classifications is crucial.
3. *Legal Interoperability (LI)* is about ensuring that organisations operating under different legal frameworks, policies and strategies are able to work together;
4. *Organisational interoperability* pertains to the capability of organisations to align their business processes, responsibilities and expectations to achieve commonly agreed and mutually beneficial goals. Organisational interoperability therefore relies on the successful interoperability of the technical, semantic and legal aspects.

This document presents the results from a first set of an internal landscape analysis to ensure compatibility of DANUBIUS-RI with other RIs. Indeed, European RIs have been working on interoperability within and across their infrastructures and have been using standards and best practices that suit their needs in terms of data management. At the European RI scale, achieving interoperability and in particular, SI requires a concerted effort to standardise data formats and metadata, adopt common vocabularies, and ontologies and data schemas, and adhere to established protocols and guidelines. In this context, the European Open Science

¹ <https://dx.doi.org/10.2799/78681>

Cloud (EOSC) is developing an Interoperability Framework (EOSC IF) to provide the procedures and services required to support a flexible framework of standards and guidelines that facilitate RI interoperability.

This document focuses on the DANUBIUS components and their links to other European RIs and a use case with the aim of providing recommendations from the component involvement and experiences in other more advanced RIs (in terms of implementation stage) for the harmonisation of DANUBIUS RI implementations. However, interoperability guidelines are currently being developed within the EOSC IF and to harmonise its implementation, DANUBIUS-RI is facing the challenge of many RI communities which have to start implementing interoperability solutions, in particular, SI solutions taking into account the diversity of approaches to implement SI and the ongoing development of EOSC interoperability guidelines. This document therefore draws recommendations to fulfil standards and best practices following the current stage of development of the EOSC Interoperability Framework.

Preliminary Landscape analysis

Rationale

The overall goal of the present internal landscape analysis is to provide a snapshot of the status, experience and literacy in interoperability of the DANUBIUS-RI components in the context of the European RIs at the time of its implementation.

We first explored the status of the DANUBIUS-RI institutions through an internal landscape analysis based on a Persistent Identifier (PID) approach, i.e. PID-graph, to identify DANUBIUS-RI institution links to other RIs and complement the WP6 landscape analysis. PIDs are key for interoperability as they provide unique and long-lasting references to entities (e.g. dataset, person, paper, institution) and are a prominent component of the European scientific ecosystem (i.e. EOSC PID policy: Hellström et al. 2020; Riungu-Kalliosaari et al., 2020). PIDs are unique references that help identify researchers, research, institutions and digital objects such as software and datasets. The ‘persistent’ in PIDs is due to the fact that even if the object they identify is moved or changed the PID will continue to resolve to the same object. This ensures traceability – that digital object can be easily located and accessed over time – and that researchers and institutions can be uniquely identified and not confused with others that share similar names. PIDs are useful because they act as pointers to an output and enable connections between different research outputs and people and organizations. These connections, or [PID Graph](#), can then become a source of information and knowledge in itself that researchers can use for discovering connections between topics or to find opportunities for collaboration. The aim of building a PID graph for DANUBIUS-RI institutions was also to provide internal recommendations for PID best practices.

An internal questionnaire on interoperability provided feedback from DANUBIUS-RI institutions on interoperability literacy and issues encountered in European projects and other RIs to identify standards and best practices currently followed in these RIs.

Finally, DANUBIUS-RI components contributed to the development of the EOSC semantic interoperability questionnaire developed by the EOSC SI Task Force in the frame of the development of the EOSC IF, by providing feedbacks to improve the questionnaire aimed at harmonising and helping European RIs converge towards common solutions and practices (Magagna et al., 2023). SI plays a central role in RIs that rely on ecosystems of interconnected services and data and are paramount in interdisciplinary research such as in DANUBIUS-RI where data from different disciplines are integrated and analysed and need to be harmonised

before being interoperated. However, there are as many semantic interoperability implementations as scientific communities and research infrastructures, and they should theoretically be interoperable.

PID graph

The benefits of PIDs can be amplified by connecting them via their metadata and PID graph specifically establishes connections between different entities within the research landscape to answer new questions about connections within the research context (Cousijn et al., 2021). For DANUBIUS-RI harmonisation, building such a graph enabled the RI to identify, at a point in time and with a standardised approach, the interconnection and potential required interoperability with identified RIs to better support collaboration. Some mature Persistent Identifier Frameworks (Datacite, ORCID, DONA, ePIC, EUDAT) are already developing technologies based on PIDs to develop PID graph (e.g. FREYA PID Graph technology, OpenAIRE Research Graph (PID graph across all sciences, org registries, author registries, funder registries)(Fenner & Aryani, 2019; Manghi et al., 2022).

Using the EXPLORE tool of the research e-infrastructure for publication OpenAIRE, we built a dataset of all papers/datasets referenced by a DOI for each researcher identified with their ORCID, of DANUBIUS-RI institution who participated to WP6 questionnaire or was cited by other researchers as contact point for other RIs within their institution ($n = 18$). To link those papers/datasets to a European project or RIs, we explored the acknowledgement section of the papers for referenced RIs and European projects cited there.

We developed a simplified PID graph inspired by the in-development PID graph (FREYA, OpenAIRE) showing links between DANUBIUS-RI institutions and other RIs through common publications using DOIs (Fig.1). Half of researchers displayed links with European projects. However, for links with other RIs, and as expected, the results appeared very heterogeneous as a function of the researcher representing the institution: 3 researchers from 2 institutions had more than 19 links with 2 other RIs (JERICO and RECETEX) and from one of these institutions, 2 other researchers have 11 and 13 links with respectively ICOS and ACTRIS. All the remaining researchers and institutions had fewer than 5 links with JERICO, ICOS, LifeWatch ERIC, eLTER, HYDRALAB, EUXINUS (the Romanian contribution to EMSO-ERIC).

The first output of the PID graph was the creation of a DANUBIUS-RI community on Zenodo to enable better connectivity of DANUBIUS-RI. Zenodo is a digital repository that allows any researcher from any domain to share and preserve any digital research output in any format and any size. Uploads are assigned a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) to allow globally unique persistent identification of the research artefact. All Zenodo data is hosted in the CERN Data Centre in the same infrastructure used for the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) data. Zenodo helps researchers receive credit by making the research results citable and through OpenAIRE integrates them into existing reporting lines to funding agencies like the European Commission. Citation information is also passed to DataCite and onto the scholarly aggregators.

CNR – ISMAR – Lucia Bongirroni
 Deltares – Ton Peters
 CzechGlobe – Karel Klem
 CzechGlobe – Jiri Koliman
 CzechGlobe – Roman Prokes
 Deltares – Anouk Blaauw
 GeoEcoMar – Adrian Stanica
 GeoEcoMar - Vlad Radulescu
 JIHOCESKA UNIVERZITA V CESKYCH BUDEJOVICICH. CENAKVA – Anna Koubová
 GeoEcoMar – Stefan Florescu
 University College Cork – Jimmy Murphy
 Deltares – Paul Van Steeg
 JIHOCESKA UNIVERZITA V CESKYCH BUDEJOVICICH. CENAKVA – Vladimir Zlabek
 TU Dresden – Thomas Grünwald
 Mareike – Ursula Braeckvelt
 HEREON - Holger Brix
 USE - Antonio Torralba
 HEREON - Yoana Voynova

Fig.1- Number of PID links between Institutions (and their representatives) and European projects and RIs. Note that EUXINUS is the Romanian contribution to EMSO-ERIC.

Interoperability survey

The WP2 DANUBIUS-IP internal survey aimed at evaluating current interoperability challenges encountered by DANUBIUS-RI institutions in other RIs to draw recommendations on current standards and best practices

followed by RIs. It helped assess the involvement of DANUBIUS-RI institutions in other RIs in relation to data management with a focus on standards, APIs and policy frameworks.

The aim of this survey was to identify common interoperability issues, challenges and current practices in the European RI ecosystem through feedbacks from DANUBIUS-RI institutions and the solutions used by other RIs to harmonise DANUBIUS-RI implementation by ensuring that DANUBIUS-RI fulfils current standards and best practices and follows the recommendations of the New EOSC (European Open Science Cloud) Interoperability Frameworks.

Design

The survey covered the 4 layers of interoperability. In particular, the questionnaire attempts to capture the breadth and scope of activities of DANUBIUS-RI institutions in other RIs where they are involved related to data:

- *generation* = creating digital data through digitising analogue data or capturing born-digital data
- *collation* = gathering independent datasets to one repository;
- *mobilisation* = enabling pre-existing digital data to become publicly findable and accessible (activities related to standards and data policy development);
- *integration* = making separate datasets an interoperable data mass (activities related to data curation and data standards);
- *distribution* = enabling data browsing, search, download and reuse;
- *annotation* = enabling crowd-sourced and expert improvement and enrichment of data with appropriate and community approved descriptors;
- *use support* = providing dashboard and/or e-Lab functions for data visualisation and analysis.

See Appendix 1.

Results

The survey was sent in April 2023 to all participants of the DANUBIUS-IP project with a deadline to send the answer on the 31st of May 2023. We received 7 answers including 3 with only negative answers. For the 4 remaining participants, 3 had to deal with the 4 types of interoperability in other RIs and/or projects, the fourth participant with organisational and legal interoperability only.

Experiences in interoperability in other RIs and projects appeared to be closely related to addressing:

- policy, privacy and security concerns (e.g. interoperability with legacy systems, licencing schemes)
- scalability and performance issues
- sustainability of PIDs and traceability concerns
- ontology selection, management and alignment taking into account semantic heterogeneity and conflict resolution (and developing mapping and crosswalk techniques)
- ensuring quality and accuracy of semantic annotations and managing evolving or non-existing ontologies.

When inquired about the interoperability challenges they faced in other RIs and projects, the most cited concepts were related to technical challenges and data (Fig.2).

persistent and resolvable identifier and machine-readable representation of each information based on a specific metadata schema.

Given that DANUBIUS-RI is currently in the implementation phase, specific questions (e.g. in which repositories does your community store, index and share metadata?) could not be answered, but the goal was also to test the clarity of the questionnaire, in order to use it with several stakeholders. However, such a questionnaire can help guide what the next steps should be to improve semantic interoperability of the (meta)data the DANUBIUS-RI community will produce, store, index and share.

Use case: Feedback and Experience of the Modelling Node CNR-ISMAR from the I-STORMS project

Context: the I-STORMS project

The Integrated sea STORM Management Strategies (I-STORMS) project was an Interreg ADRION project completed in 2020 based on open and standard interoperability principles to enhance data sharing and access to advanced functionalities. It tackled the territorial challenges linked to the lack of shared information and know-how on sea storms, poor macro-regional cooperation, low data interoperability, lack of coordination and exchange on civil protection procedures in the context of sea storm emergencies, warning systems and civil protection procedures and climate change. It gave an emphasis on harmonisation activities of existing practices within the framework of the EU Policy for the Adriatic-Ionian Macro Region (EUSAIR) and the EU civil protection mechanism. The aim was to enhance transnational cooperation sharing knowledge, data and forecasts through a common infrastructure, joint strategies to deal with sea storm emergencies, improving at the same time countries' capacities on data interoperability, early warning and civil protection procedures, in alignment with the EU Civil Protection Mechanism. The innovative approach on data sharing, the common guidelines on early warning and civil protection, the transnational strategy, and the permanent cooperation table was set to ensure that current challenges are faced and overcome in the framework of EUSAIR and with a medium-term implementation perspective.

The use case of the DANUBIUS Modelling Node-CNR-ISMAR

One of the partners of the DANUBIUS Modelling Node - CNR ISMAR was a partner in the I-STORMS project with the task of developing the software infrastructure named *I-STORMS web systems (IWS)*. The infrastructure is still operational and has been improved with software update and other components in the STREAM Project (Italy – Croatia Interreg Project). In the I-STORMS project, CNR ISMAR followed the Service-Oriented Geoportals Architecture approach (De Longueville, 2010; Yang et al., 2007) that combines interoperable standard services with high level Graphical User Interfaces. As such CNR ISMAR mainly dealt with technical interoperability to develop the interoperable infrastructure for accessing and sharing sensor data and forecasts together with geographic data.

The IWS design is based on existing open source software: the geonode Framework allows to manage geospatial data and metadata and share them. The aim of the IWS was to foster data and information sharing between multi-users communities in a context of high heterogeneity of data (e.g. time series of meteorological observations, vector data), data models (e.g. multidimensional model outputs), formats and infrastructure. In this context, CNR ISMAR encountered the following challenges:

- Ensuring interoperability while allowing the current existing systems to stay in place by keeping the operational workflows

The common data sharing system was designed to collect daily several (up to 15) forecast models and create a single ensemble model – TMES (Ferrarin et al. 2020). The solution adopted was to use a custom software (see below) to process each source with a fine-grained configuration based on expert judgment. Information are required about source grid and coordinate systems, original variable names, sea level reference and astronomical tide and also the metadata about modelling engine and meteo forcing and credential for different servers. At the moment add or replace one source model require a big effort and sometimes the workflow stops if some of the sources are unavailable or misconfigured.

In application-level interoperability, the ability of an application to utilise multiple distributed heterogeneous resources is becoming increasingly important with increasing volumes of data and multiple sources of data as well as resource types.

- Heterogeneous format of the data, metadata and data models with the objective to foster the partners' capacities to deal with required data standards at EU level and beyond.
- PID assignment to datasets
- Tracking of the number of users who use the services which is crucial in terms of cost justification to governments and also to encourage other partners to join the service provision

Their solutions were based on partners' involvement at all phases, common data policy, common agreed data structure e.g. observation of oceanic measurements, open source framework (e.g. published on github public repositories) and codes and custom software development. One solution to overcome the lack of semantic interoperability pertained to partner nodes involvement through agreed requirements (e.g. deposit the datasets following a common convention for file names, directories and data format (e.g. CSV, netCDF CF)). Therefore, they designed a Common Data Sharing System designed to collect data from different partner's nodes and provide access to the stored resources through standardised interfaces (e.g. OGC-Web service, web API). In this system, the sharing of the data occurs through 4 steps, each relying on open codes (e.g. python), standardised data formats (e.g. json files) and services (e.g. XML web services). In particular, in the first step "Data harmonisation", data from partner nodes are processed by web services that apply the same structure to measurements. All data are then made available to the geoportal GUIs through standard web services (e.g. OGC web services).

Through the I-STORMS project, CNR ISMAR also contributed to the harmonisation and interoperability between partners, institutions, RIs and countries by following and applying the Open Data principles of open format and licensing: e.g. codes are published on github public repositories (<https://github.com/CNR-ISMAR/iws>), for the whole infrastructure (Geoportal and storm atlas) <https://iws.seastorms.eu>; <https://github.com/CNR-ISMAR/mmes>, for the ensemble creation is published daily on a thredds.data server instance available at iws.tools4msp.eu, a piece of software was developed by eLTER to harmonise LTER data <https://cnr-ismar.github.io/econaos/>; <https://github.com/CNR-ISMAR/econaos/tree/master/code>

Currently, no solutions were found for PID assignment to datasets and for user tracking.

Recommendations and Best Practices

Overcoming the multiple interoperability challenges requires increasing common knowledge of interoperability but also, the use of innovative tools, services and approaches with a continuous and strong support of interoperability experts. In order to address the technical and semantic challenges effectively, a

deeper understanding of practices within communities is essential as it can help identify successful approaches, their locations, their application, and their underlying motivations. Developing use cases and standardised surveys could help spot gaps and ways to overcome them in practice. In the best case, this leads to a deep change in practices within communities, such as improving existing tools, publishing metadata schema and semantic artefacts in machine readable format and enhancing their adoption and efficient use. To gain such understanding, the EOSC SI TF is starting to engage with various communities and collect information through a landscaping exercise leveraging a survey described in the previous section. Open dialogue, researcher involvement and cross-community initiatives appear paramount: events such as FAIR Implementation Profile workshops have proved useful to facilitate cross-community convergence in the selection of semantic artefacts.

In terms of technical interoperability for the design of services and provision of data access, an RI such as DANUBIUS-RI needs to account for the numerous scientific applications and users that will use data and local resources but also for data and resources coming from other infrastructures and networks with varying speeds and characteristics. It is therefore paramount to avoid as much as possible, to design applications and services tightly coupled to specific resource types and technologies and to think about estimated frequency of access, transferred volumes, number of concurrent users, total number of users at an early stage of implementation. In designing services and applications, the approach further needs to be as user-oriented as possible: services and applications must be user-friendly without requiring full understanding of conceptual and technical backgrounds, retrocompatible, and easily adaptable to different programming environments. Many technical challenges are being encountered, e.g. regarding the scalability of softwares, code versioning and optimisation, hardware requirements, data access, that limit technical interoperability.

These technical challenges are parts of the aspects that the DANUBIUS Modelling Node considers for the common future work to develop with all the modellers of the DANUBIUS Consortium. In order to increase the interoperability of the codes used, to be applied in a large range of cases and adopted by the highest number of institutions, the scalability and the hardware compatibility should be addressed with common approaches for different model codes. Moreover, there is the need to increase the use of open source codes in order to overcome problems of licencing and further use. The Modelling Node represents a common place for the modelling community in river-sea systems to exchange best practices and try to find common approaches to increase interoperability. In the past years, the Modelling Node started this activity organizing a set of workshops (on standardization of model outputs and post processing procedures). In the future also the above challenges will be discussed to find best practices to adopt.

Adoption of PID is one of the key indicators of community awareness and literacy in interoperability requirements (see David et al., 2020). Having a network of interconnected PID systems as “PID Graphs” makes it easier for a RI in the implementation phase (e.g. DANUBIUS-RI) to identify connections with other RIs. Through interlinked research objects, such network brings together all entities linked in some way through a particular publication or other research “endpoint”, and helps identifying where efforts to automate the flow of information between systems is and will be needed and where computerized information exchange between systems will be needed. PID graphs can also be used in monitoring the RI connections in the European RI landscape. They can improve speed and accuracy in reporting by providing a standardised visualisation of DANUBIUS–RI interoperation status within the European project landscape and DANUBIUS-RI links to other RIs, in the process of sharing research outputs. They can also lead to discovery and innovation by exposing for instance the links between those research outputs. It is also of paramount importance that DANUBIUS-RI gets a ROR (Research Organisation Registry) when it will become an ERIC. For the same objective, we created a Zenodo community for DANUBIUS-RI: while not being equivalent to a PID, the Zenodo community will enable researchers to link DANUBIUS-RI to other research projects.

The European Interoperability Framework highlighted the lack of necessary in-house data steward skills as a barrier to implementing interoperability policies. The European Interoperability Framework recommended that member States include interoperability skills in their interoperability strategies, acknowledging that interoperability is a multi-dimensional issue that needs awareness and skills in legal, organisational, semantic and technical. For this to happen in a sustainable way, it is essential that at local levels such as the RI level, training and capacity building to improve literacy regarding interoperability is organised (David et al., 2023c). For DANUBIUS-RI, our internal questionnaire highlighted a gap in interoperability knowledge and understanding with 3 participants (including partners from the WP on data management) answering that they had never had to deal with any type of interoperability. In order to address these technical challenges effectively, a deeper understanding of interoperability practices within specific communities is essential as a base to develop them and this is even more true for RIs involved in interdisciplinary research. DANUBIUS-RI needs to identify such skills within its consortium to ensure communication and coordination between experts, in the view of starting the harmonisation of its implementation and fostering interoperability at this early stage. We also point out, in agreement with the Biodiversa+ project (D2.2, Basset et al., 2022), that lack of both specialized and experienced sources of qualification are obstacles in finding skilled human resources. EOSC has started to develop workshops and resources on training (e.g. EOSC FUTURE Train-The-Trainer⁴, EOSC Synergy⁵) but it is paramount that at the RI level, training on interoperability is organised to ensure key partner literacy. Acknowledging this, we organised a training webinar on semantic interoperability in collaboration with EOSC-LIFE (David, Madon et Torralba, 2023) and more are needed to foster a smooth implementation of interoperability principles at DANUBIUS – RI level. However, researchers need to participate in dedicated training and workshops and this requires awareness, incentives and reward mechanisms. The development of training schemes on interoperability must therefore be foreseen with rewards for researchers and communities in order for them to contribute actively in community driven practices, e.g. for ensuring data quality and accuracy, particularly when integrating data from multiple sources (David et al., 2023c).

Finally, in an effort to link DANUBIUS-RI to other RIs and projects aimed at improving interoperability at the European scale, we collaborated with researchers of the EOSC-Life project⁶ on a paper dedicated to EOSC-Life's lessons and recommendation for sustainability (David et al., 2023d). Although based on sustainability of RIs in the life science, many recommendations apply also to interoperability challenges such as:

[R4] Plan training for acute and future needs: *Developing competent, effective and sustainable training methodologies and formats within the scope of an inclusive cross-disciplinary Open-Science framework is a stepwise, evolutionary process. It requires: a) connecting experts, trainers and users in a goal-oriented manner, such as through open calls, b) creating adaptive platforms with resources that promote targeted dissemination and the exchange of knowledge, enabling a rapid response to the needs of different communities, and c) providing sufficient sustainable funding schemes to keep this network of experts active and functional beyond time-limited tasks. Making investments in sustaining competent human resources and training is essential to ensure the uptake of tools, services and solutions and to integrate other expertise and diverse communities.*

[R5] Metadata makes FAIR: *Repositories or portals hosting scientific digital objects in a semantically interoperable manner or collections of physical material (biobanks, culture collections) that provide sufficient provenance and other FAIR (meta)data with the objects they share are becoming more trusted sources of scientific resources, promoting their use in the community. For this reason, guaranteeing provenance is*

⁴ <https://eoscfuture.eu/eventsfuture/train-the-trainer-an-active-learning-course-on-understanding-using-eosc/>

⁵ <https://www.eosc-synergy.eu/>

⁶ <https://www.eosc-life.eu/>

recommended to ensure the practical sustainability of scientific objects and the services that provide them, i.e. allowing sustainability through re-use.

[R6] Be prepared, agile and act timely: *Agility is often forgotten but is required to address emerging challenges, and this is particularly true in the LS. EOSC-Life has applied its action plan, which has a high level of adaptability, in order to be able to anticipate and provide non-centralized services and expert support during the COVID-19 crisis. To ensure sustainability, we must proactively take advantage of all relevant opportunities. One key lesson learned through the EOSC-Life Open Calls was the high importance and value of facilitating interactions and regular exchange between domain-specific experts and project teams. This approach triggered an early uptake of available tools and knowledge, and also activated effective, collaborative and timely co-development of targeted solutions and guidelines, spreading across disciplines.*

[R7] Curate NOW: *EOSC-Life has invested in projects which prioritise, leverage and extend expert curation processes. These projects build capacity, adding value to existing data and delivering processes which can be re-used and combined with automated techniques for data annotation. The provision of high-quality, curated datasets is also essential for the development of new AI and data-driven initiatives and projects in LS research. Assessing the efficiency of quality processes could help to improve research outputs.*

[R9] Harmonise and integrate: *It is easier to encourage the long-term adoption of new operating systems by potential users when these can be connected with previously issued products, and if these are backwards compatible with previously issued tools, scripts and software. Harmonisation, reached by iterative consensus, facilitates and guarantees the interoperability of tools, data and solutions, and improves the understanding of concepts, functionalities and semantics shared across communities and disciplines. It is also easier to maintain services if they are fully integrated into the relevant communities' ecosystems.*

[R10] Reward sustainability: *Further efforts and investments of resources devoted to increasing sustainability are often considered as unprofitable in the short term. They should, however, be promoted and rewarded as a means of increasing the quality of products and when they are recognized by users as being essential. Rewarding contributors for their extra efforts and making them visible in the community contributes to success and cohesion.*

[R11] Be open AND be inclusive: *Open specifications of data formats and data exchange protocols promote trust and inclusiveness and safeguard against obsolescence. Inclusiveness is critical to maintaining interest, increasing adoption, and integrating newcomers who can sustain and reuse solutions and tools. Community building is a key component for long-term training, good data-sharing literacy and efficient project output dissemination and reuse.*

Conclusion

The cross-RI interoperability solutions will range from working out common infrastructure reference models, technologies, taxonomies, ontologies, controlled vocabularies (to improve data governance) and recommendations to practical matters such as use of common services, metadata discovery, scalability. Achieving interoperability is a complex task that involves various challenges, ranging from understanding different types on interoperability concepts, to technical and societal challenges for its successful implementation. This complexity needs to be tackled at different scales: at the European scale, DANUBIUS-RI will need to deploy some of the EOSC interoperability guidelines to achieve interoperability for integration

of its to resources (e.g. data, services) within the EOSC-Core. In parallel, more initiatives such as the Italian project ITINERIS⁷ need to be developed to foster harmonisation at the national levels. Finally, at the RI level, more human resources such as data stewards, working groups and committees such as the one we created for DANUBIUS-IP in WP2, are required to grasp each RI specificity and challenges in order to link them with the national and European efforts for improving interoperability and harmonization of the European RI landscape.

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Appendices

Appendix 1 – Interoperability Survey

Deadline: **31 May 2023**

When completed to be returned as a **pdf file** to: **bgcmadon@us.es**

The results of the survey will be anonymously incorporated into the Use Case report (D.2.1).

Context

This survey is part of Task 2.2. to ensure compatibility with other ERICs and RIs and ensure that DANUBIUS-RI fulfils current standards and best practices, following the recommendations of the New European and EOSC Interoperability Frameworks. The aim of this survey is to identify common interoperability challenges in the RI ecosystem through feedbacks from DANUBIUS-RI partner institutions.

Please provide as much details as possible (contextual data, when relevant: concerned dataset/digital object persistent identifier (PID), year...)

For “Yes/No” answer below, remove the non-pertaining option!

Participant details

First Name(s):

Surname(s):

Participant’s Institution (involved in DANUBIUS):

Contact Email:

I- Have you ever had to deal with interoperability and if so, which level(s) and field(s) of interoperability?

1- Legal interoperability

which is about “ensuring that organisations operating under different legal frameworks, policies and strategies are able to work together”

- A. With legal data use conditions (ex: issue with data sharing: licensing scheme, with data linkage and with management): **Yes/No**
- B. With the legal conditions for the creation and use of combined or derivative products: **Yes/No**
- C. With user legal access and use each dataset without seeking authorization from data rights holders on a case-by-case basis, assuming that the accumulated conditions of use for each and all of the datasets are met: **Yes/No**
- D. With Compliance with GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation): **Yes/No**
- E. With other: **Yes/No**

2- Organisational interoperability

Which refers “to the way in which public administrations align their business processes, responsibilities and expectations to achieve commonly agreed and mutually beneficial goals”.

- A. With data management plan (DMP): **Yes/No**
- B. With data policy: **Yes/No**
- C. With persistent identifiers (PIDs): **Yes/No**
- A. With standard compliance: **Yes/No**
- D. With standard development: **Yes/No**
- E. With other: **Yes/No**

3. The semantic interoperability

Which ensures that “the precise format and meaning of exchanged data and information is preserved and understood throughout exchanges between parties”.

- A. with data and related semantic artefacts (include ontologies, terminologies, taxonomies, thesauri, vocabularies, metadata schemas and standards): **Yes/No**
- B. with mapping and workflows (i.e. the transformation of data from one form to another to enable the involved systems to work in collaboration): **Yes/No**
- C. with persistent identifier (PIDs): **Yes/No**
- D. with standard development: **Yes/No**
- E. With other: **Yes/No**

4. The technical interoperability

Which covers “the applications and infrastructures linking systems and services. Aspects of technical interoperability include interface specifications, interconnection services, data integration services, data presentation and exchange, and secure communication protocols”.

- A. with data brokerage (providing links between identifier systems, creating links where there is no other source and providing links that can be curated by the community): **Yes/No**
 - B. with data linkage and schema language: **Yes/No**
 - C. with middleware (i.e. an intermediary between heterogeneous systems that converts sent messages between systems from one form to another or to a standard form that is understood by all cooperating parties): **Yes/No**
 - D. with wrapper (which works to wrap legacy systems in a layer that enables interaction with these systems by providing intermediaries between external systems and the legacy system): **Yes/No**
 - E. with Translator (often used at the level of applications (between the sender and the receiver) so that the data is translated from one form to another to be understood by the receiving party, which could be a one-way or bi-way translator): **Yes/No**
 - F. with Application Programming Interfaces (APIS): **Yes/No**
 - G. with Distributed Digital Archive: **Yes/No**
 - H. with service development and implementation: **Yes/No**
 - I. With other: **Yes/No**
- 5. None: Yes/No**

II- For which research infrastructure or project did you deal with interoperability?

(for each, please specify project/research infrastructure names – provide project/RI PIDs if available:

- 1- For legal interoperability:
- 2- For organisational interoperability:
- 3- For semantic interoperability:
- 4- For technical interoperability:

III- Which challenges did you encounter?

- 1- In scalability, complexity, and data redundancy.
- 2- In privacy, licencing and security issue in the open data or with cooperation (e.g. overcoming organizational resistance to sharing data)
- 3- In implementing the I (Interoperable) of the FAIR principles:
- 4- In the lack of standardization and harmonisation schemas across data sources:
- 5- In the lack of ontology
- 6- In ubiquitous computing, context-awareness
- 7- In configuring and collecting services/applications in a centralized environment to create new applications (e.g. issues with original cloud in security, support, network...).
- 8- In processing old data, and transforming it into a standardized format to enable its interaction with modern systems.
- 9- In managing inconsistent information across multiple sources
- 10- In handling data movement and the encryption of data
- 11- In defining cloud interoperability
- 12- other:

Thank you very much!